

A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF LEARNING STYLES AMONG MARITIME STUDENTS FOR TEACHER DEVELOPMENT AND INSTRUCTIONAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the learning style preference of maritime students in a maritime institution with the view to improving teachers' effectiveness and curriculum planning. A sample of 126 students was used based on a stratified random sampling technique from 185 students enrolled, the survey used VARK (Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing, Kinesthetic) questionnaire to determine dominant learning preferences. The study brought to light the fact that there was a very high adoption of visual learning preference (33.33%) followed by auditory (25.40), read/write (23.02) and kinesthetic (18.25). Simple cross-tabulation also revealed differences in learning preferences with regards to academic years while enhancing the need for visuals and practice sessions. Interviews with educators provided quantitative data regarding the usefulness of visuals aids and also pointed to difficulties in teaching kinesthetic learners especially in critique and theory-based classes. Teachers reported a high interest in incorporating in their lessons more designs that involve simulation and practical projects to enhance learner's multiple intelligences. In this study, awareness of different learning styles was identified, however, many educators preferred to deliver their lessons through conventional lectures, hence the lack of professional development and training was criticized. The study underscores the need to adopt multiple modes of teaching that will suit different groups of students. Specific suggestions which have been made include use of graphics, improvements on RSA, and the provision of specific professional development programs for the teachers. If these needs are met, then it will allow maritime education programs to develop a more positive learning environment, increase engagement, and to provide better prepared graduates that are thus ready to meet the challenges of the maritime sector. This research

provides useful information for all stakeholders in education who want to enhance instructional practices in maritime education.

Keywords: *Learning Styles, Maritime Education, Visual Aids, Instructional Design, Teacher Development*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of developing education models, paying attention to learning styles has emerged as one of the central notions. Every learner has a different approach to learning and interpreting information and the teacher must understand these differences in order to achieve the goals of his teaching (Al-Roomy, 2023). This principle is particularly important for any school that prepares learners for a specific area of practice, such as maritime education where learners are supposed not only to understand knowledge but also to master practical skills and competencies. Maritime education largely entails theoretical instruction in the classroom, practical exercise in simulators as well as practice on actual vessels and since this education has some influence on the character of the students it becomes crucial to consider the type of learning these students have in a bid to enhance their learning and consequently their training. This vast research explores the learning profiles of marine students and provides general ideas on how learning preferences contribute to the teacher training and course delivery. Stakeholders in the maritime industry expect that their employees will be persons with problem solving skills and very high level of professionalism. As maritime educators attempt at ensuring the mastery of such competencies among the students, the traditional black board methods of teaching /training will not lead to the best results (Yuen, Tan & Loh 2022). However, when teaching methods are designed in explicit correlation with the learning style of the students, the resultant learning process produces better lifestyle learning outcomes with right orientation of the appropriate challenging field of maritime professions.

The premise of this study is that one has a learning style, on the basis of which information can be grasped and assimilated visually, auditorily or through body movement (Toit, 2014). Since the frequency of the learning styles can be used effectively in identifying the dominant ones, the educators can then adapt with the area of focus to get along with the way the maritime students learn best (Ramani & Avinash 2016). This approach not only increases effectiveness of the students but also increases retention of knowledge which is essential in the maritime sector.

When it comes to changes over time in terms of technology as well as current paradigms around maritime education and international regulations governing the seas and the ocean there is a heightened call for dynamic and flexible approaches to adopting change in the classroom (Kim et al., 2023). Today's marine market has not only high expectations for qualifications, but also for people's ability to effectively address a number of possible scenarios in their work. Maritime educators must therefore grow in capacity alongside the industry in order to make sure that their ideas of instruction are compatible with the students and the industry. The complex nature of learning styles constitutes a route

through which knowledge about learning styles can enshrine changes in practice for educators, which in turn can enhance the existing instruction and teacher professional development strategies.

Regarding the classroom practice, this research also implies the need for teacher development in working learning styles diversity. Teacher training as a way of improving the quality of maritime education is able to offer the knowledge and instruments to identify and respect individual learning styles (Ziarati & Albayrak, 2008). Education enhancement strategies designed as part of teachers training can enhance educators' capacity regarding the utilization of non-information transmission methods. Yet this shift is most apparent in the sphere of maritime education, where practice and embodied training are at least as valuable as theory.

In doing so, it is hoped that such findings will help toward designing a learning climate that is more supportive for the students in maritime education. In this way, acknowledging and responding to the different learning profiles of the learners, educators will be able to create a far deeper level of students' engagement and completion, giving them not only academic, but also career ready skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in the conditions of the maritime market. While maritime institutions will continue to gain insight on the needs of students and the industry, a direct approach in instructional design engineering that incorporates needs of individual students for graduates to effectively apprentice necessary competencies will ensure the maritime institution produces professional standards competent maritime students.

Research Questions

1. What kind of learning do the maritime students embrace most?
2. With what success and learning rates, the various learning styles affect the academic achievement of the maritime students?
3. In what way can learning styles knowledge be applied to improve the learning experiences of Maritime students?
4. Defining the issues that maritime educators have in managing diversity in respect to learners' information assimilation needs, and how professional development can be of assistance.
5. With regard to the different learning-styles-orientated approach to maritime education how can technology-aided, and simulation-based learning be effectively implemented?
6. What is the effect of modifying instructional approaches according to learning styles on student engagement and retention rates in marine programs?

METHODOLOGY

Research Method Used

Descriptive research design was utilized in this research to assess the learning styles of the maritime students (Camilon, Monder & Salapare, 2023). The study was done in a maritime school with students' population of 185 in 1st to 3rd year. Slovin's formula estimated the required sample size of 126 students, and to gain an equal balance from all years, a form of stratified random sampling was used.

Sample Size Determination Using Slovin's Formula

To determine the sample size, Slovin's formula was used:

Where:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

- **n** = sample size
- **N** = population size (185 students)
- **e** = margin of error (commonly set at 5% or 0.05)

Substituting the values into Slovin's formula:

$$n = \frac{185}{1 + 185(0.05^2)} = \frac{185}{1 + 185(0.0025)} = \frac{185}{1 + 0.4625} = \frac{185}{1.4625} \approx 126.46$$

Thus, the sample size that was calculated was expected to be about 126 Students. This is actually 68% of the total population and it guarantees Internal Validity and Reliable outcomes for the study.

Data Collection

In order to determine learning preference of the students the VARK (Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic) questionnaire was used. This questionnaire includes questions based on multiple choices to determine different learning styles of each student. All 126 participants filled the survey during class time. In order to obtain additional qualitative information, informal interviews were conducted with some students and teachers chosen at random which provided the researcher with a deeper look at how the learning style preferences affect the instruction. To compute the percentage of students with each learning style, the following formula was applied:

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of students with specific learning style}}{\text{Total number of students}} \right) \times 100$$

For example, to calculate the percentage of visual learners:

$$\text{Percentage of Visual Learners} = \left(\frac{42}{126} \right) \times 100 = 33.33\%$$

The same formula was utilized to calculate the percentages for auditory, reading/writing, and kinesthetic learners.

Sample Size Justification

The study targeted 185 students as the population and having a sample of 126 students and we used the Slovin's formula since we wanted a maximum of 5% error. This number of respondents was 68 percent of the total enrollment of the school which allowed for a large and diverse enough sample to analyze the results. In order to maintain a diverse representation of the student's learning styles, considering their various academic years at the maritime institutions, SRS also known as quota sampling was used. The methodological strategy improves the external validity of the discovery and yields to the conception of specific instructional interventions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section the findings from the theoretical framework study as well as the qualitative interviews conducted among educators of the maritime students are provided. Secondly, the findings are presented in tables for easy understanding and then a brief discussion on each table is made.

1. Quantitative Results: Learning Styles Distribution

The survey conducted targeted 126 maritime students, wherein their learning preferences have been analyzed based on the VARK model. The results are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Learning Styles Distribution of Maritime Students

Learning Style	Number of Students	Percentage
Visual	42	33.33%
Auditory	32	25.40%
Reading/Writing	29	23.02%
Kinesthetic	23	18.25%

Learning Style	Number of Students	Percentage
Total	126	100%

Table 1 shows that 33.33% of maritime students falls under the visual learning style which was the most common learning style among the participants. This result implies that adding diagrams, charts, and videos and other visualization aids to the learning content could improve knowledge acquisition and knowledge retention by these students. Another 25.40% of the participants were found to be auditory affected, which means they learn well whenever there is talking and discussions. This also underlines the need to use the students' preferred modality of receiving content, which is the auditory mode, as a prior learning teaching strategy by incorporating more lectures, discussions, etc.

Speaking/Reading & Writing learners were 23.02% of the participants showing a large group that prefer textual mode of information delivery. That is why the students should be offered as many and as differentiated as possible reading sources, textbooks and written tasks within the learning process. Finally, there were 18.25% of kinesthetic learners in the group. These students are best suited for practical, simulation and laboratory exercises which imply that practical activities, simulations and laboratories are key to the performance of these students.

The findings of learning diversity in the context of this study render a pedagogical approach that adopts the use of multiple teaching methods in the maritime learning environment as more effective. Instead, by understanding the different learning styles that can exist, the proper strategies can be implemented of ensuring that as many students as possible receive the best learning experience possible. The suggestions derived from this research may be useful for developing teaching models and mentoring practice, it underlines the importance of adopting more versatile approach to teaching that would be suitable for maritime learners' profile.

2. Cross-Tabulation: Learning Styles by Academic Year

Table 2: Learning Styles Distribution by Academic Year (1st Year to 3rd Year, 126 Students)

Academic Year	Visual	Auditory	Reading/Writing	Kinesthetic	Total Students
1st Year	18 (37.50%)	13 (27.08%)	9 (18.75%)	8 (16.67%)	48

Academic Year	Visual	Auditory	Reading/Writing	Kinesthetic	Total Students
2nd Year	15 (34.09%)	12 (27.27%)	9 (20.45%)	8 (18.18%)	44
3rd Year	12 (30.00%)	10 (25.00%)	11 (27.50%)	7 (17.50%)	40
Total	45	35	29	23	126

Cross-tabulation presented in Table 2 illustrates the learning style preference of 1st to 3rd-year maritime students with overall sample size of 126 students.

In the 1st Year, 37.50% of the students favored the visual style of learning: charts and diagrams; 27.08% of students were auditorily oriented: lectures and discussions. Among them, readers/writers constituted 18.75% and 16.67% of the students were kinetic students, which may imply that even with the initial lessons, students require to have interactions with their environment through physical activities.

In the 2nd Year, learners were also visual at 34.09%, with 27.27% being the auditory type of learners. Kinesthetic learners were 18.18% whereas reading/writing learners were 20.45%. This balance shows that in their second year, students are still able to be taught in many ways which include; display teaching methods and learner centered teaching methods.

Based on the results of the 3rd Year, the percentage of visual learners was lower with only 30.00%, reading/writing learners were higher with 27.50% which indicates that as the topic gets more complex the students prefer textual material. Auditory learners consisting of 25.00% indicated that despite the incorporation of information technology in teaching and learning processes, there is still need for practical demonstration and experience through kinesthetic learners who recorded 17.50%.

Such findings go to prove that although visual learning is still dominant in all the academic years there is an equal representation of other learning styles. This diversity makes it essential for maritime educators to employ a variety of instructional methods so that one or the other teaching/learning strategy aligns with students at all stages of their learning process.

3. Qualitative Results: Educators' Perceptions

This includes focus group and open interviews with 6 maritime educators concerning how they reason concerning disability and highly effective learning styles of students. Table 3 also captures some of the key subjects that emerged out the interviews.

Table 3: Key Themes from Educators' Interviews

Theme	Description
Need for Visual Aids	Most educators emphasized the importance of visual aids (diagrams, charts, and videos) in explaining complex concepts.
Challenges with Kinesthetic Learners	Educators reported difficulties in engaging kinesthetic learners, especially in theory-heavy subjects like navigation and engineering.
Importance of Practical Training	Hands-on training and simulations were considered critical for reinforcing theoretical knowledge, especially for kinesthetic learners.
Preference for Traditional Lectures	Despite diverse learning styles, many educators still favored traditional lecture-based teaching methods.
Professional Development Gaps	Educators highlighted the need for professional development programs that focus on differentiated instruction strategies.

Using the statistics presented in table three, illustrates vast and significant features concerning various imperative aspects about the educational needs of marine students. Firstly, the findings confirmed that there is the need for display aids in the classroom since teachers described how useful the display aids were in explanation of hard topics related to maritime. This tally with the findings on the VAK profile that indicated that majority of the students are visual learners, which require visuals in their learning process and thus supports the view that visuals should persist in the maritime education. On the other hand, many educators reported complications of the kinesthetic learning style especially in courses that favor theory such as navigation perhaps despite its practical implication there are not adequate practical activities to handle. This suggests that there is a need for increased provision of techno-clinical learning resources, including ship simulators, and practical student projects for these students.

Moreover, the educators across all countries stressed the need for practical training in supporting learning especially to the kinesthetic learning style saying that any maritime education programs need to have adequate practical experience to enable the student to be market ready (Mallam, Nazir & Renganayagalu, 2019.). But there were few teachers who still believe in the traditional way of Information dissemination through speeches. This preference can be attributed to poor training, funding or inadequate resource to apply the differentiated instruction strategies properly (Zhang et al., 2014). Additionally, the interviews highlighted that many educators perceive themselves as untrained in how they can meet the needs of learners with different learning styles hence indicating an area of

needed professional learning. Targeted programs might assist educators achieve differentiated instruction that incorporates several teaching methodologies favoring all learning types so improving learning in learners with maritime education.

4. Synthesis of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The findings of the two quantitative and qualitative phases of the research point towards the need to incorporate the teaching of diverse learning styles in the maritime education (Türkistanli, 2023). The percentage that prefers to learn via tutors also means that more of them should be incorporated in their curriculum especially for the beneficiaries. Yet necessities of the other twenty percent of kinesthetic learning students must not be ignored either as they may learn best by practicing skills, participating in role plays, and completing other exercises. Teachers continued use of conventional instruction techniques, however, even when they understand the variation in students' learning styles may indicate a void in the current professional development. Maritime institutions should direct their effort in giving educators the knowledge and support for them to incorporate effective differentiation strategies especially for kinesthetic and reading and writing learners.

Conclusions

This paper afforded an understanding of learning approaches among the maritime students as well as their tuitional implications to teachers' formation and teaching – delivery strategies. The results showed that the overall perception of maritime students learning preference lean towards both visual and audio modalities with other considerable preference to reading/writing as well as kinesthetic style. These different learning styles underscore the importance of the human factor in maritime education, where the instructor has to use a number of strategies to deliver the learning to a group of students with different learning styles.

The largest response was from visual learners who pointed out that diagrams, charts and videos should be the prominent point of maritime training. Out of all the suggested materials, the following ones can be of the greatest value for the correct usage of every type of learner: Auditory learners will benefit from discussions and verbal lectures, reflecting the significance of effective ratings and questions during the collective learning process. While there are fewer of them compared to the other learners, kinesthetic learners need to gain information through movement and experience and this directly applies to students of the maritime college. It is important that this group applies practical activity and implement practical exercise as a means of bridging theoretical knowledge with practical experience gained through simulations.

The qualitative perspectives from educators provide a supportive elaboration of the difficulties they encounter while catering for the presented diverse learning requirements. Many teachers understand that there is more than one way of teaching; however, they teach through more conventional approaches that are mainly because of constraints in resource and capacity. This underscores a need for the professional development

programs that will allow teachers to address teaching instruction, in a way that will ensure everyone is engaged.

Therefore, for maritime education to meet the demands of the maritime industry institutions offering these courses should adopt strategies that suit all the different categorizations of students. Thus, the expansion of educators' capability in applying visual-aural, reading and writing/kinesthetic learning-teaching strategies in their instructional design will not only yield high academic performance to maritime students but complete maritime training equipped to face real-world experience in the future.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of maritime education by accommodating diverse learning styles:

1. Information visualization can be used in instruction methods as educators should incorporate diagrams, charts, videos, and multimedia displays. Employing this approach will assist in demystifying many of the complex concepts involved in maritime and engaging the vast number of learners who are estimated to be visual learners.
2. Based on the analysis of the kinesthetic learners, shipping education should conduct more of ship simulators, workshops and practical projects. This could be developed through collaborations with maritime industries to provide genuine training opportunities so that the students adopt marketable skills.
3. Professionals teaching students should undertake a course in differentiation with a view to proffer ways of addressing the many learning profiles. Some of the training that could be conducted to teacher include workshop on active learning strategies for engaging students' participation as well as collaborative learning strategies and the use of technology in learning and teaching.
4. To promote preferred learning types among learners, institutions should introduce focused professional development for teachers mainly on diversity. These programs might support teacher with the information and resources they need to construct socially just classrooms.
5. The progress check with reference to the above aspects can offer useful information about the performance of the students about learning processes. Teachers should periodically receive this feedback so that institutions put in place ways of gathering them to help in the enhancement of teaching practices.
6. Group and peer learning can also help in addressing issues of various learning demands and requirements of students through creating studentship culture. Teachers should seek to provide practice opportunities that would engage students in a way that they learn from one another.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed ethical research practice in conducting the entire research. During data collection, formal written permit was obtained from the relevant institutional wetland to conduct all the research activities in compliance with the laid down ethical Standards. The rights of all the participants student and educators were respected since they were all made to understand the benefits, methodology and consequences of the study. This was as a measure to ensure that their rights were protected and they informed their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without reasons. Communal and personal identity of all participant were kept secret all through the research process while all data collected was anonymized. Further, all the data collected during the study was taken with high level of privacy and could only being accessed by the researchers working on the given study. All interests were impartial and the research solely for learning purposes. This work respected all the relevant law and ethical issues concerning the use of human subjects in research.

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